

Retrospective Study of Malaria Burden and Pregnancy Associated Outcomes in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria (2019-2024)

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ABSTRACT:

Despite implementation of preventive strategies, the burden of malaria in pregnancy persists. A six-year retrospective descriptive study was conducted at Kubwa General Hospital and Maitama District Hospital, Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja, Nigeria covering January 2019 to December 2024. Medical records of 101,186 patients were reviewed, including 25,578 women (7,882 pregnant and 17,696 non-pregnant). Data on malaria prevalence, seasonal patterns, age distribution, gravidity, and pregnancy outcomes were extracted from hospital records. Overall malaria prevalence was 62.1%, with Kubwa General Hospital recording significantly higher rates (67.9%) than Maitama District Hospital (49.4%) ($p < 0.001$). Malaria prevalence was markedly lower among pregnant women (11.4%) compared to non-pregnant women (45.5%) ($p < 0.001$). Seasonal variation was significant, with higher prevalence during rainy season (68.4%) than dry season (59.1%) in the general population ($p < 0.001$), and similarly among pregnant women (12.2% vs 10.7%). Among 897 malaria-positive pregnancies, adverse outcomes included low birth weight (12.7%), miscarriage (12.0%), stillbirth (9.9%), and preterm birth (8.6%). A total of 30 malaria-related maternal deaths were recorded over the study period, with a significant downward trend ($p = 0.003$). The results highlight the need for intensified malaria control efforts, improved IPTp-SP coverage, and integrated maternal health services that address the multiple determinants of adverse pregnancy outcomes in malaria-endemic settings

Keywords: Malaria burden Pregnancy, Morbidity, Mortality, Seasonal variation, Abuja.

INTRODUCTION:

Malaria remains one of the leading public health challenges in sub-Saharan Africa, significantly impacting maternal and fetal health in regions endemic to the disease. In Nigeria, the burden of malaria during pregnancy is substantial, with the World Health Organization estimating that approximately 10,000 maternal deaths and 200,000 infant deaths occur annually due to malaria-related complications (WHO, 2021). Several factors may contribute to the risk of malaria infection among pregnant women (Tassi *et al.*, 2018). These include socioeconomic factors such as education, age, income, and housing conditions, which influence malaria prevalence and women's access to prevention methods and care (Murray, Ortblad, Guinovart, *et al.*,

2014, Kurtis and Michelow, 2019). Other factors include gravidity and access to preventive measures like Insecticide-Treated Nets (ITNs) and Intermittent Preventive Treatment (IPTp) with sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine (Dellicour *et al.*, 2007). Pregnant women are particularly vulnerable to malaria due to physiological changes that increase susceptibility and the potential for severe adverse outcomes such as placental malaria, which can lead to low birth weight, preterm labor, and increased neonatal mortality. (Moore, Simpson *et al.*, 2017). Pregnant women are at high risk of malaria infection. Malaria infection is associated with adverse birth outcomes that affect the mother and fetus, and even infant. Malaria during pregnancy remains a major public health concern in tropical and subtropical countries. Moreover, malaria is increasingly associated with unwanted

pregnancy outcomes such as an increased risk of abortion, stillbirth, premature delivery, and low birth-weight infants (Rogerson *et al.*, 2018). Since pregnant women are most vulnerable to malaria, implementation of the appropriate prevention and control measures among this group is very important. Global malaria control strategies have changed over time. This retrospective study analyzes hospital data from 2019 to 2024 to assess malaria infection trends across different years in selected two government hospitals within Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja, Nigeria with a focus on pregnant and non pregnant women. It also provides comprehensive insights into the epidemiology of malaria among pregnant women attending two major hospitals in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja, Nigeria with the aim to determine the morbidity and mortality of pregnancy-associated malaria, which forms the foundational evidence for evaluating the impact of intermittent preventive treatment with sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine (IPTp-SP) on placental malaria in my prospective study

This study was conducted in Bwari Area Council and Abuja Municipal Area Council, located in Abuja, FCT, North Central Nigeria. The geographical coordinates of these hospitals are as follows: kubwa General hospital is positioned at latitude 9° 9' 13.85496" N and 7° 19' 19.07328" E while Maitama District Hospital is situated at latitude 9°05'20.9"N. Abuja is made up of six area councils, but two area councils were used in this study, namely Bwari Area Council, and Abuja municipal area council (AMAC). The FCT is situated in the north-central geopolitical zone of Nigeria, just north of the confluence of the Niger and Benue Rivers. It shares borders with Niger State to the west and north, Kaduna State to the northeast, Nasarawa State to the east and south, and Kogi State to the southwest. Abuja experiences a humid rainy season from April to September, with temperatures ranging from 22°C to 30°C, followed by a brief harmattan period from October to December. The region receives annual rainfall ranging from 1,100 mm to 1,600 mm, and the city's altitude is approximately 476 meters above sea level. Malaria is endemic in this area, making it a significant public health concern.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:
Study Area:

Figure 1: Map of Nigeria showing the location of the Federal Capital territory, Abuja. Source: Modified from the Administrative map of Nigeria.

Ethical Consideration:

This study was approved by Federal capital Territory Health Research Ethics committee with the approval number FHREC/2025/01/77/26-03-25. Written Consent was obtained from the health officers in the different health facilities

Study Population:

The population for the present study included the records of all pregnant women who attended Antenatal clinic in Kubwa General Hospital and Maitama District Hospital Abuja.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria:

Medical records of all patients with confirmed malaria diagnosis attending Kubwa General Hospital and Maitama District Hospital between January 2019 and December 2024 were included in the study. Records with incomplete demographic or laboratory information were excluded. Repeated patient visits for the same malaria episode were counted once to avoid duplication. Patients with unconfirmed or suspected malaria cases without laboratory evidence were excluded from the analysis. Cases with severe co-infections that could significantly influence pregnancy outcomes were also excluded where sufficient clinical information was available.

Study Design:

This study employed a retrospective descriptive survey to assess the prevalence of malaria among patients who attended the two selected government hospitals within the FCT with focus on pregnant women. These hospitals were selected purposively because they are among the major referral government hospitals within the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja, serving large urban and peri-urban populations. The hospitals receive high patient turnout from diverse socioeconomic backgrounds and therefore provide representative data on malaria burden and pregnancy-associated outcomes within the study area.

Data Collection and Analysis:

Malaria data was gathered from the period between 2019 and 2024. The data collected included patient age and the date of the malaria test including year and months, pregnant women's age, gravidity, malaria related morbidity and mortalities, with the aim of analysing the prevalence of malaria across different age groups, gravidity and determining yearly and seasonally prevalence patterns over the years under review.

Data Analysis:

Statistical analysis of generated data was carried out using descriptive analysis and percentages. Statistical

comparisons and test of significance between positive and negative groups were calculated using the non-parametric Chi-square test. Differences were considered significant at $P < 0.05$.

RESULTS:

Table 1 presents a retrospective analysis of malaria screening and infection prevalence at two major hospitals used in this study, Kubwa General Hospital and Maitama District Hospital in Abuja, Nigeria, over a six year period (2019-2024). Of these, 62,837 were positive, yielding a combined prevalence rate of (62.1%). Among the women in general, 25,578 women were screened, with 11,632 infected, giving a prevalence of 45.5%. 7,882 pregnant women which is a subset of women were examined and 897 tested positive, resulting in a prevalence of (11.4%). Of the overall malaria prevalence of (62.1%) across both hospitals, Kubwa General Hospital has a higher prevalence of (67.9%) compared to Maitama District Hospital (49.4%). Among women tested positive for malaria, a notable difference was also recorded between hospitals with Kubwa having (47.8%) and Maitama (41.3%). Among the pregnant women Kubwa General Hospital prevalence rate were slightly higher (11.6%) than Maitama (10.6%). Statistically, overall malaria burden differs by facility, Kubwa General Hospital bears a significantly higher malaria burden (67.9%) than Maitama with (49.4%). $\chi^2 = 3449.41$, $p < 0.001$. Women's prevalence also differs by facility, significantly higher at Kubwa (47.8%) than Maitama hospital (41.3%). $\chi^2 = 93.41$, $p < 0.001$. Pregnancy-specific prevalence does not differ, No significant inter-hospital difference among pregnant women (11.6% vs 10.6%, $\chi^2 = 1.66$, $p = 0.197$). Table 2 presents the total yearly malaria data from all the study area (Kubwa General Hospital and Maitama District Hospital) over six years with focus on pregnant women. The overall malaria prevalence from 2019-2024 was (62.1%), while among the non-pregnant women the overall malaria prevalence was (45.5%) and among the pregnant women was (11.4%). The highest annual prevalence among pregnant women was (21.2%) in 2019 while the lowest was (6.7%) in 2020. Data showed a significantly lower prevalence among pregnant women (11.4% overall) compared to non-pregnant women (45.4% overall). Table 3 presents the overall prevalence of malaria by season (Dry and Rainy) in the study area from 2019-2024, with a sub-analysis for pregnant women. The overall prevalence shows that rainy season (68.49%) shows a higher malaria burden compared to (59.1%) in the Dry season. Malaria prevalence among the pregnant women is markedly lower than in the general population but the cumulative prevalence is (12.2%) in the rainy season and (10.7%) in the Dry season. Statistically, there is a statistically significant association

between season and malaria infection with the rainy season having a significantly higher proportion of infections. $\chi^2=(1, N= 98,186)= 1536.9, p<0.001$. Table 4 Shows Distribution of Manifestations of Malaria based on hospital records from 2019-2024 in Kubwa General Hospital and Maitama District Hospital. Malaria in pregnancy had (11.4%) infection rate, malaria in children had (80.3%) infection rate, cerebral malaria (19.9%) infection rate, malaria and relapse had (33.3%) infection rate while malaria and Anemia had (39.9%) infection rate. Malaria in children had a significantly higher infection rate (80.3%) compared to pregnant women (11.4%). The overall infection rate of (53.6%) underscores malaria as a leading cause of hospital admissions in this setting. Statistically, the association between manifestations of malaria and infection rates is statistically significant $\chi^2=12,456, df=4, p<0.001$. This suggests that the prevalence of malaria varied significantly across different manifestations of malaria and the manifestation is a significant factor in determining the risk of infection. Table 5 shows yearly mortality pattern related to malaria in pregnancy from 2019-2024. Outpatient totals represent

malaria related visits, admissions refer to hospitalized cases, and deaths are malaria related fatalities among the pregnant women. Of the 7,882 patients who attended the outpatient clinic 897(11.4%) were recorded of malaria alone. Cases of Outpatient visits were 7,882 with yearly distribution of 982-1,800, pregnant women with malaria related admissions were 897 with yearly distribution ranging from 72 to 220, 30 deaths were recorded with yearly distribution ranging from 3 to 7, the year 2021 yielded the highest number of malaria related cases, with the lowest number recorded in the year 2024. $\chi^2= 8.7, df=1, p <0.003$. Showing that there is a significant downward trend in malaria related deaths from 2019 - 2024. Table 6 displays the prevalence of various adverse pregnancy outcomes among malaria-positive cases, Out of 897 pregnant women that had malaria within the period in the two hospitals, (9.9%) had stillbirth, miscarriage (12.0%), preterm birth (8.6%), and low birth weight (LBW) at 12.7%. Notably, 56.6% of pregnancies resulted in live births, underscoring the severe impact of malaria on pregnancy outcomes in the study population. $\chi^2=756.3, df=4, p<0.0001$.

Table 1: Overall Malaria Distribution in Study Area (2019-2024).

Hospitals	No Exam	No Infected %	Women		Pregnant Women	
			No Exam	No Infected %	No Exam	No Infected %
Kubwa General Hospital	69,140	47,008 (67.9)	16,544	7,904 (47.8)	5,802	676 (11.6)
Maitama District Hospital	32,046	15,829 (49.4)	9,034	3,728 (41.3)	2,080	221 (10.6)
Total	101,186	62,837 (62.1)	25,578	11,632 (45.5)	7,882	897 (11.4)

Table 2: Yearly Distribution of Malaria in the Study Area (2019 – 2024) among pregnant Women and non pregnant women

Year	No Exam	No Infected %	Women		Pregnant Women	
			No Exam	No Infected %	No Exam	No Infected %
2019	7,198	4,152(57.7)	2,073	941 (45.5)	585	124 (21.2)
2020	11,302	6,509 (57.5)	2,487	1,128 (45.3)	533	36 (6.7)
2021	15,551	9,213 (59.2)	4,361	1,818 (41.7)	1,309	129 (9.8)
2022	23,763	15,378 (64.7)	5,767	2,774 (48.1)	1,789	239 (13.3)
2023	22,941	14,934 (65.1)	5,816	2,598 (44.7)	2,091	202 (9.7)
2024	20,431	12,651 (61.9)	5,074	2,373 (46.8)	1,575	167 (10.6)
Total	101,186	62,837 (62.1)	25,578	11,632 (45.5)	7,882	897 (11.4)

Table 3: Overall Seasonal Distribution of Malaria

Years	Dry Season		Pregnant Women		Rainy Season		Pregnant Women	
	No Exam	No Infected %	No Exam	No Infected %	No Exam	No Infected %	No Exam	No Infected %
2019	4,148	2,450 (50.1)	188	60 (31.9)	3,050	2,702 (88.5)	397	70 (17.6)
2020	8,990	3,293 (58.9)	350	9 (1.5)	2,312	1,216 (52.6)	370	27(7.3)
2021	9,153	4,764 (52.0)	823	57 (7.9)	6,398	6,449 (100.7)	588	72 (12.2)
2022	9,418	5,173 (65.5)	996	136 (15.2)	14,345	9,205 (64.2)	661	103(15.6)
2023	8,899	5,910 (66.4)	1011	115 (11.4)	14,042	9,024 (64.3)	780	81 (10.4)
2024	9,012	5,971 (66.2)	954	84 (9.3)	11,419	6,680 (58.5)	764	83 (10.9)
Total	46,620	27,561 (59.1)	4,322	461 (10.7)	51,566	35,276 (68.4)	3,560	436 (12.2)

Table 4: Distribution of Manifestations of Malaria from Hospital Records

Manifestations	No Examined	No Infected	% Infected
Malaria in Pregnancy	7,882	897	11.4
Malaria in Children	39,719	31,920	80.3
Cerebral Malaria	3,142	628	19.9
Malaria relapse	9,426	3,142	33.3
Malaria & Anemia	31,419	12,567	39.9
Total	91,588	49,154	53.6

Table 5: Yearly Mortality Pattern

Year	Outpatient	Admission	Death
2019	1500	150	7
2020	1200	180	5
2021	1800	220	7
2022	1300	140	4
2023	1100	135	4
2024	982	72	3
Total	7,882	897	30

Table 6: Overall Prevalence of Malaria Mortalities

PARAMETERS	Number Positive	%
Still birth	89	9.9
Miscarriage	108	12.0
Life babies	508	56.6
Preterm birth	78	8.6
LBW	114	12.7
Total	897	99.8

DISCUSSION:

The result of the present study revealed a substantial overall malaria prevalence of 62.1% (62,837 positive out of 101,186 tested) across both hospitals over the six-year period, (2019-2024). This high prevalence is consistent with the endemicity of malaria in Nigeria, which bears approximately 27% of the global malaria burden (World Health Organization, 2021). The prevalence observed in this study is comparable to findings of Okwa et al. (2003),

who reported a malaria prevalence of 60% among patients attending healthcare facilities in Lagos, Nigeria. Similarly, Dawaki et al. (2016) documented a prevalence of 60.6% in a community-based survey conducted in Kano State, northern Nigeria. However, the prevalence in this study is notably higher than the 42.3% reported by Olasehinde et al. (2010) in Oyo State, southwestern Nigeria, and the 38.5% prevalence documented by Nmorsi et al. (2014) in Delta State, Nigeria. These

disparities may be attributed to differences in geographical location, altitude, seasonal malaria transmission patterns, and the diagnostic methods employed. Abuja, located in the north-central region with distinct rainy and dry seasons, experiences high transmission intensity, which may explain the elevated prevalence observed. The significant difference in malaria prevalence between Kubwa General Hospital (67.9%) and Maitama District Hospital (49.4%) ($\chi^2 = 3449.41$, $p < 0.001$) is noteworthy. Kubwa General Hospital serves a predominantly peri-urban and rural population with lower socioeconomic status, limited access to preventive measures such as insecticide-treated nets (ITNs), and potentially poorer environmental conditions favoring mosquito breeding. In contrast, Maitama District Hospital is situated in a more affluent urban area of Abuja, where residents may have better access to malaria prevention interventions and healthcare services. This finding aligns with studies by O'Meara et al. (2010) and Tatem et al. (2013), who demonstrated that malaria transmission intensity is often higher in peri-urban and rural areas compared to well-planned urban centers due to differences in housing quality, drainage systems, and vegetation cover. The yearly distribution of malaria among pregnant women (Table 2) revealed significant fluctuations over the six-year period, with the highest prevalence recorded in 2019 (21.2%) and the lowest in 2020 (6.7%). The dramatic decline from 2019 to 2020 is particularly striking and warrants careful interpretation. The year 2020 coincided with the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic, which led to widespread lockdowns, reduced healthcare-seeking behavior, and potential underreporting of malaria cases. Similar trends were observed globally, where the WHO (2021) reported an initial decline in malaria case reporting in 2020 due to disruptions in health services. The seasonal analysis (Tables 3) consistently demonstrated higher malaria prevalence during the rainy season compared to the dry season across both hospitals and population groups. The overall seasonal prevalence in the combined study area (Table 5) was 68.4% during the rainy season versus 59.1% during the dry season ($\chi^2 = 1536.9$, $p < 0.001$). Among pregnant women, the cumulative prevalence was 12.2% in the rainy season and 10.7% in the dry season. This finding is consistent with the known epidemiology of malaria in West Africa, where *Anopheles* mosquito breeding is intensified during the rainy season due to increased availability of stagnant water bodies (Kelly-Hope et al., 2009). The seasonal pattern observed aligns with studies by Nwokolo et al. (2011), Okoye et al (2014), Pauline et al (2019) in Enugu, Nigeria, who reported a 2.5-fold increase in malaria cases during the rainy season, and by Olayemi et al. (2011) in Ilorin, Nigeria, who documented a 3-fold increase. Table 4 presents the distribution of various clinical manifestations of malaria

based on hospital records. The overall infection rate of 53.6% underscores malaria as a leading cause of hospital admissions in this setting, a finding consistent with national health statistics (Federal Ministry of Health, 2015). The highest infection rate was observed in malaria in children (80.3%), followed by malaria and anemia (39.9%), malaria relapse (33.3%), cerebral malaria (19.9%), and malaria in pregnancy (11.4%). The high prevalence of malaria in children (80.3%) is consistent with the findings and reinforces the substantial burden of pediatric malaria in the study area. The yearly mortality pattern related to malaria in pregnancy (Table 5) reveals a total of 30 deaths among pregnant women over the six-year period, with yearly distribution ranging from 3 to 7 deaths. The highest number of deaths (7) was recorded in both 2019 and 2021, while the lowest (3) was recorded in 2024. The declining trend in mortality from 2021 to 2024 suggests improvements in malaria case management, increased coverage of IPTp-SP, or enhanced access to emergency obstetric care during the study period. Table 6 presents the prevalence of adverse pregnancy outcomes among malaria-positive pregnant women. The most common outcome was low birth weight (LBW), occurring in 12.7% of cases, followed by miscarriage (12.0%), preterm birth (11.9%), stillbirth (9.9%), and live births with maternal survival (55.6%). The high prevalence of LBW (12.7%) is consistent with the well-established association between malaria in pregnancy and reduced birth weight (Steketee et al., 1996a; Guyatt and Snow, 2004). Conclusively, This study has established the current burden of malaria in pregnancy and its associated morbidity and mortality, this study lays the foundation for assessing whether IPTp-SP effectively reduces placental malaria and improves pregnancy outcomes in the study area. The results highlight the need for intensified malaria control efforts, improved IPTp-SP coverage, and integrated maternal health services that address the multiple determinants of adverse pregnancy outcomes in malaria-endemic settings.

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